

Heterocycles derived from 2-*N*-Acetyl-*N*-2,5-dichlorophenylthiazole-4-aldehyde

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In our previous communications¹, we reported the synthesis of 2-*N*-acetyl-*N*-2,5-dichlorophenylthiazole-4-aldehyde (1) with the synthesis of some dibenzodiazepines¹ and biologically active quinazolinyltriazoles^{2,3} derived from 1. In view of this encouraged results we wish to report some new heterocycles derived from 1.

The thiosemicarbazone (2) when refluxed with acetic anhydride afforded the thiadiazole⁴ (3). Compound 2 when treated with 1,3-dichloroacetone gave the thiazolyl hydrazone (4) (Scheme 1). Cyclisation of 4 with acetic anhydride afforded the triazolothiazole (5) with *N*-acetylation and acetylation in deactivated thiazole ring. The aminothiadiazo⁵ (6) was obtained by lead tetraacetate oxidation of 2. 4-Phenylthiosemicarbazone (7) upon oxidation with ferric chloride in presence of methylene chloride gave the thiadiazole⁶ (8) which showed nmr peaks at δ 3.5 and 3.72 suggesting chloromethylation due to solvent methylene chloride and catalyst ferric chloride, in the thiazole and *N*-phenyl ring. Also the protons of *N*-phenyl ring appear as AB quartet in nmr spectra. Schiff base obtained from 4-chloro-*o*-aminophenol and 1 was converted to the benzoxazole⁷ (9) by lead tetraacetate in presence of methylene chloride and potassium carbonate. Reaction of 1 with homopiperazine gave 1,5-diazabicycloheptane⁸ (10). The dibenzodiazepine¹ (11) derived from 1 and 12 was treated with lead tetraacetate in presence of methylene chloride, potassium carbonate and acetic anhydride. In either cases the diazepine ring was hydrolysed to yield 12 which cyclised to 13 and 14 respectively, under the experimental conditions.

Experimental

All the m.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir (KBr) spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 599B spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a Varian (360 MHz) instrument. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses. The thiosemicarbazones (2 and 7) were prepared by the reported methods.

4-Acetyl-2-acetylamino- Δ^2 -5-(4'-thiazole-2'-*N*-acetyl-*N*-2'',5''-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazoline (3): The thiosemicarbazone (2; 1 g, 0.0026 mol) and acetic anhydride (5 cm³) were refluxed together for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature, poured over ice-water, extracted with methylene chloride, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and evaporated under reduced

pressure. The resulting solid was crystallised from acetonitrile (52%), m.p. 225° (Found: C, 43.27; H, 3.20; N, 15.03, C₁₇H₁₅Cl₂N₅O₃S₂ requires: C, 43.22; H, 3.18; N, 14.83%); ν_{\max} 1 690, 1 710, 1 610, 1 420 and 1 400 cm⁻¹; δ 2.0 (3H, s, N-COCH₃), 2.02 (3H, s, N-COCH₃), 2.5 (3H, s, NHCOCH₃), 6.6 (1H, s, H-5) 7.0–7.8 (4H, m, ArH) and 8.0 (1H, s, NH).

2-Acetyl-5-chloromethylthiazolo-(1,2,4-triazolo)-3-(2'-*N*-acetyl-*N*-2'',5''-dichlorophenyl-5'-acetyl)thiazole (5): The thiosemicarbazone (2; 1 g, 0.0026 mol) was refluxed with 1,3-dichloroacetone (0.33 g, 0.0026 mol) in acetone for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, excess acetone was evaporated and the resulting semisolid was refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 cm³) for 3 h. After cooling, the mixture was poured to ice-water, extracted with methylene chloride, washed with sodium carbonate, dried and passed through a silica gel column (15 g) and eluted with chloroform. The crude solid obtained from chromatography was crystallised from carbon tetrachloride, (41%), m.p. 165° (Found: C, 44.05; H, 2.97; N, 12.96. C₂₀H₁₄Cl₃N₅O₃S₂ requires: C, 44.08; H, 2.94; N 12.86%); ν_{\max} 1 690, 1 610, 1 470 and 1 400 cm⁻¹; δ 2.00 (3H, s, C₅'-COCH₃), 2.06 (3H, s, N-COCH₃), 2.09 (3H, s, N-COCH₃), 2.2 (2H, s, CH₂Cl), 6.6 (1H, s, H-3) and 7.0–8.0 (4H, m, ArH).

2-Amino-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl-5-(2'-*N*-acetyl-*N*-2'',5''-dichlorophenyl)thiazole (6): To the thiosemicarbazone (2; 1 g, 0.0026 mol) dissolved in methylene chloride (25 cm³), were added potassium carbonate (1.8 g, 0.013 mol) and lead tetra-acetate (1.15 g, 0.0026 mol) with stirring. The reaction mixture was further stirred at room temperature for 5 h, when initially it turned green and then slowly to a brown solution. This solution was then poured over ice-water, filtered, extracted with methylene chloride, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and evaporated. The resulting solid was recrystallised from carbon tetrachloride, (42%), m.p. 232° (Found: C, 40.31; H, 2.43; N, 18.1. C₁₃H₉Cl₂N₅O₃S₂ requires: C, 40.42; H, 2.33; N, 18.14%); ν_{\max} 3 090, 3 000, 2 970, 2 940, 2 880, 1 680, 1 580, 1 530 and 1 470 cm⁻¹; δ 2.0 (3H, s, N-COCH₃), 3.6 (2H, s, br, NH₂, exchangeable with D₂O) and 7.20–8.20 (4H, m, ArH).

2-*N*-(*p*-Chloromethyl)phenylimino-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl-5-(2'-*N*-acetyl-*N*-2'',5''-dichlorophenyl-5'-chloromethyl)thiazole (8): To a suspension of the thiosemicarbazone (7; 1 g, 0.0022 mol) in methylene

NOTES

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) $NH_2NHCSNH_2$, (ii) Ac_2O , (iii) $ClCH_2COCH_2Cl$, (iv) $LTA/CH_2Cl_2/K_2CO_3$, (v) $NH_2NHCSNHPh$, (vi) $FeCl_3/CH_2Cl_2$, (vii) 4-chloro-2-aminophenol, $LTA/CH_2Cl_2/K_2CO_3$ and (viii) 1,4-diazocycloheptane.

chloride (30 cm³), was added hydrated ferric chloride (1.18 g, 0.0044 mol) with stirring. The solution was further stirred at room temperature overnight. The reaction mixture was then washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and concentrated. The resulting solid was recrystallised from acetonitrile, (43%), m.p. 237° (Found: C, 45.09; H, 2.70; N, 12.61. C₂₁H₁₅Cl₄N₅OS₂ requires: C, 45.08; H, 2.68; N, 12.52%); ν_{\max} 1 670, 1 610, 1 510, 1 440 and 1 430 cm⁻¹; δ 2.0 (3H, s, N-COCH₃), 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂Cl), 3.72 (2H, s, CH₂Cl), 6.14 (1H, s, C₅-H) and 6.8—7.75 (7H, m, ArH).

2'-(N-Acetyl-N-2'',5''-dichlorophenyl)-4'-thiazolyl)-2-(5-chloro)benzoxazole (9): A mixture of the thiazole aldehyde (1) and 4-chloro-*o*-aminophenol in equimolecular quantities, was heated in methanol in presence of traces of acid. The mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid was filtered and recrystallised from methanol and utilised for the next step. To this compound (1 g, 0.0023 mol) dissolved in methylene chloride, was added potassium carbonate (1.66 g, 0.012 mol), followed by lead tetra-acetate (1.02 g, 0.0023 mol) under stirring. The reaction mixture initially turned green and then slowly brown. Stirring was continued for 5 h. The mixture was then poured into water, filtered, extracted with methylene chloride, washed with sodium bicarbonate and water, dried and evaporated. The resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol, (52%), m.p. 215° (Found: C, 49.17; H, 2.30; N, 9.57. C₁₈H₁₀Cl₂N₃O₂S requires: C, 49.26; H, 2.28; N, 9.58%); ν_{\max} 1 680, 1 570, 1 480, 1 470 and 1 400 cm⁻¹; δ 2.0 (3H, s, N-COCH₃) and 7.4—9.7 (7H, m, ArH).

8-(2'-N-Acetyl-N-2'',5''-dichlorophenyl)thiazol-1,5-diazabicyclo[3,2,1]octane (10): To a solution of 1,4-diazacycloheptane (homopiperazine) (0.32 g, 0.0032 mol) in ethanol, was added a solution of the aldehyde (1; 1 g, 0.0032 mol) in ethanol. The resulting mixture was agitated for 15—20 min during which the mixture became warm, and was stirred at room temperature overnight. After removal of the solvent, the crude product was recrystallised from ethanol, (52%), m.p. 215° (Found: C, 51.40;

H, 4.59; N, 14.19. C₁₇H₁₈Cl₂N₄OS requires: C, 51.39; H, 4.53; N, 14.11%); ν_{\max} 1 690, 1 580, 1 520, 1 400 and 1 370 cm⁻¹; δ 1.8 (1H, dt, 3*a*), 0.9 (1H, dt, 3*e*), 1.96 (3H, s, N-COCH₃), 2.83 (4H, m, C₆-H, C₇-H), 2.7 (4H, m, C₄-H, C₂-H), 4.8 (1H, s, C₈-H) and 7.05—7.06 (4H, m, ArH).

The tetrahydrodibenzodiazepine derivative (11) was synthesised as per procedure reported earlier¹. Reaction of 11 with lead tetra-acetate in presence of methylene chloride and potassium carbonate under conditions similar to 6 afforded compound 13. Also reaction of 11 with acetic anhydride under conditions similar to 3 gave compound 14: 1,2,3,4,12-pentahydro-2,2-dimethylphenazin-4-one (13) (Found: C, 73.78; H, 7.09; N, 12.32. C₁₄H₁₆N₂O requires: C, 70.68; H, 7.02; N, 12.28%); ν_{\max} 3 040, 2 920, 2 860, 1 700, 1 610, 1 540, 1 470, 1 480 and 1 400 cm⁻¹; δ 1.16 (6H, s, C(CH₃)₂), 2.84 (2H, s, CH₂C=N), 3.4 (4H, m, CH₂CO, CH and NH, NH exchangeable with D₂O) and 7.8—8.3 (4H, m, ArH); 1,2,3,4,12-pentahydro, 2,2-dimethyl-5-acetyl-phenazine-4-one (14) (Found: C, 71.25; H, 6.70; N, 10.3. C₁₆H₁₈N₂O₂ requires: C, 71.11; H 6.67, N, 10.37%); ν_{\max} 1 690, 1 640, 1 580, 1 540, 1 500 and 1 470 cm⁻¹; δ 1.0 (6H, s, C(CH₃)₂), 2.16 (3H, s, N-COCH₃), 2.5 (3H, s, CH₂C=N), 3.39 (2H, s, CH₂CO), 4.5 (CH) and 6.4—7.8 (4H, m, ArH).

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